

Supplementary Materials for “Synthetic Networks That Preserve Edge Connectivity”

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S1 Real-World Networks

We studied 110 different undirected networks of different types including citation, social, biological, informational, economic, and technology. Of these, 104 were selected taken from Netzschleuder [3], a network catalogue. The 104 networks from Netzschleuder are:

academia_edu; dbpedia_producer; hyves; plant_pol_robertson;
advogato; dbpedia_recordlabel; inploid; polblogs; anybeat;
dbpedia_starring; interactome_figeys; power; at_migrations;
dbpedia_team; interactome_stelzl; prosper; berkstan_web;
dbpedia_writer; interactome_vidal; bible_nouns; dbtropes_feature;
internet_as; reactome; bibsonomy; digg_votes; jdk; bitcoin_alpha;
discogs_label; jester; slashdot_zoo; bitcoin_trust; dnc;
jung; sp_infectious; bookcrossing; douban; lastfm_aminer;
stackoverflow; drosophila_flybi; libimseti; stanford_web;
elec; linux; topology; chess; email_enron; livemocha; twitter;
chicago_road; email_eu; lkml_reply; twitter_15m; citeseer;
epinions; lkml_thread; uni_email; citeulike; epinions_trust;
marker_cafe; us_air_traffic; escorts; marvel_universe;
visualizeus; movielens_100k; wiki_article_words; faa_routes;
myspace_aminer; wikiconflict; nematode_mammal; wiki_link_dyn;
collins_yeast; fediverse; netscience; wiki_rfa; cora;
flickr_groups; new_zealand_collab; corporate_directors;
fly_hemibrain; dblp_cite; openflights; dblp_coauthor_snap; foldoc;
dbpedia_country; github; wiki_users; dbpedia_genre; google;
paris_transportation; word_assoc; dbpedia_location; google_plus;
petster; wordnet; dbpedia_occupation; google_web; pgp_strong;
yahoo_ads; eu_procurements; notre_dame_web; python_dependency;
slashdot_threads; facebook_wall; fly_larva;

We also included six other datasets used in prior studies [2], with the last five available in the SNAP repository [1]:

- Curated Exosome Network (CEN), a citation network of 13,989,436 nodes and 92,051,051 edges, constructed from the literature on exosome research [4].

- Cit-HepPh, a citation network of Arxiv High Energy Physics papers containing 34,546 nodes and 420,877 edges;
- Cit-Patents, a network of citations among US patents containing 3,774,768 nodes and 1651,8947 edges;
- Orkut, a social media network containing 3,072,441 nodes and 117,185,083 edges;
- Wiki-Talk, a network of 2,394,385 nodes and 4,659,565 edges, capturing users and discussions on Wikipedia from its inception until January 2008; and
- Wiki-Topcats, a web graph of 1,791,489 nodes and 25,444,207 edges of Wikipedia hyperlinks collected in 2011.

These 110 networks vary significantly in size, ranging from roughly 1,000 nodes to 13.9 million nodes, and varying from 2000 to 117 million edges.

S2 Network comparison evaluation criteria

We outline the evaluation criteria, network properties and distance metrics, adopted for comparing network properties between synthetic and empirical networks in Table S1.

Table S1. Key Network Properties and Distance Metrics

Statistic	Type of Statistic	Distance Metric
Minimum Edge cuts	Sequence	RMSE
Diameter	Scalar	Relative Difference
Mixing Parameter	Scalar	Simple Difference
Degree	Sequence	RMSE
Ratio of disconnected clusters	Scalar	Simple Difference
Global Clustering Coefficient	Scalar	Simple Difference
Mean Local Clustering Coefficient	Scalar	Simple Difference
Number of Cluster Edges	Distribution	Kolmogorov-Smirnov Distance
Edges between Outliers & Clustered Nodes	Scalar	Relative Difference
Outlier Node Degree	Sequence	RMSE

S3 RECCS Workflow and Algorithms

The complete flow of Step 1 of RECCS is visualized in Figure S1.

Fig. S1. RECCS Workflow. The two phases of Step 1 of RECCS pipeline, which modifies an initial network (which has no singleton clusters) by adding edges to improve its fit to the input parameters. The first phase uses the input parameters (clustering, degree sequence, number of edges within and between clusters, and edge connectivity for each cluster) and adds edges to the starting network to achieve the required edge connectivity, and the second phase adds edges to improve the fit to the degree sequence.

In Stage IV Version 1 of RECCS, *RECCSv1*, edges are randomly added between nodes with available degrees, meaning nodes in the synthetic network with degrees lower than corresponding degrees in the real-world network G . Specifically, if we have a set of nodes $\mathcal{S}$ of size l where each node s_i has an available degree d_i where $i \in [1, l]$, edges are added connecting these nodes using Algorithm 1.

In Stage IV Version 2 of RECCS, *RECCSv2*, edges are added to nodes with available degrees, taking into account the number of inter-cluster and intra-

Algorithm 1 RECCS Phase 2 : Version 1

Require: $length(S) \geq 0$

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1: Initialize:
2:  $available\_node\_degrees \leftarrow \{node : degree \mid node, degree \in S\}$ 
3:  $max\_heap \leftarrow available\_node\_degrees$ 
4: while  $max\_heap$  is not empty do
5:    $(avail\_degree, available\_node) \leftarrow \text{heapq.heappop}(max\_heap)$ 
6:   if  $available\_node$  not in  $available\_node\_degrees$  then
7:     continue
8:   end if
9:   Find  $available\_non\_neighbors \leftarrow \{available\_node\_degrees : node \mid node \neq$ 
 $neighbor\_of\_available\_node\}$ 
10:   $avail\_k \leftarrow \min(avail\_degree, \text{len}(available\_non\_neighbors))$ 
11:  for  $i$  in  $range(avail\_k)$  do
12:     $random\_node \leftarrow \text{random}(available\_non\_neighbors)$ 
13:    Add edge  $(available\_node, random\_node)$ 
14:    Delete  $random\_node$  from  $available\_non\_neighbors$ 
15:    if  $available\_node\_degrees[random\_node] > 1$  then
16:       $available\_node\_degrees[random\_node] -= 1$ 
17:    else
18:      Delete  $random\_node$  from  $available\_node\_degrees$ 
19:    end if
20:  end for
21:  Delete  $available\_node$  from  $available\_node\_degrees$ 
22: end while

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cluster edges in the input graph G . This approach, detailed in Algorithm 2, restricts the addition of edges to not exceed the expected number of inter cluster edges.

Algorithm 2 RECCS Phase 2: Version 2

Require: Empirical graph G , Synthetic network $N_{intermediate}$ (SBM generated network modified by RECCS Stages 1-3), Clustering $\mathcal{C}$

- 1: **Initialize:** Read G , $N_{intermediate}$ and $\mathcal{C}$
 - 2: Calculate the inter cluster and intra-cluster edge probabilities matrix $probs_{emp}$ based on G and $\mathcal{C}$
 - 3: $available_node_degrees \leftarrow \{node : degree \mid node, degree \in S\}$
 - 4: Calculate the synthetic edge probabilities matrix $probs_{syn}$ for $N_{intermediate}$
 - 5: Compute the difference matrix $\Delta P = probs_{emp} - probs_{syn}$
 - 6: Restrict diagonal and negative values in ΔP to 0
 - 7: Identify clusters with no *available_nodes* and set the corresponding rows and columns in ΔP to zero.
 - 8: Compute $available_nodes \leftarrow available_node_degrees.keys()$
 - 9: Compute degree sequence $\mathcal{D} \leftarrow available_node_degrees.values()$
 - 10: Compute cluster assignment $\mathcal{C}'$ for *available_nodes*
 - 11: Generate new graph N' using SBM with $\mathcal{C}'$, ΔP , and $\mathcal{D}$ as input
 - 12: Remove parallel edges and self-loops in the generated network N' .
 - 13: $N_{output} \leftarrow N_{intermediate} + N'$
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S4 Outlier Strategies

In this section, we explain each of the outlier strategies proposed in the paper.

Given a network G , its clustering $\mathcal{C}$ with L non-singleton clusters and the set of nodes that do not belong to any cluster (outlier nodes), we now focus on creating a synthetic version of the subnetwork G^* of G , that has for its edge set outlier edges defined as those edges that have at least one endpoint that do not belong to any non-singleton cluster, which can connect either two outlier nodes or one outlier node and one clustered node. Note that G^* includes clustered nodes as well as outlier nodes. It has the same set of clusters as in $\mathcal{C}$, but there are no edges within any non-singleton cluster, and no edges between any two non-singleton clusters.

We propose three strategies for this problem in the main paper. Each takes the input parameters computed from G^* and $\mathcal{C}$ to generate a network N^* consisting of outlier edges.

It is important to note that G_c , the subnetwork of clustered nodes, can be modelled separately with SBM or any other network generator that preserves node and cluster correspondence. The resultant network N_c combined with N^* will give the final synthetic network N that has all the nodes of G .

S4.1 Outlier Strategy 1

This approach has each outlier in its own block, and then passes all the parameters computed for G^* to SBM to generate a network. Recall that these parameters include an assignment of nodes to blocks, with each of the given non-singleton clusters a block, so that now there are k additional blocks. Thus, if there are k outliers, then there are $L + k$ total blocks. Note that there is either 0 or 1 edges between each pair of outlier clusters, indicating whether or not there is an edge between the two outliers. It then passes the clustering, assignment of nodes to clusters, and numeric parameters for G^* to the SBM software to generate a random graph. Note that this approach reproduces exactly the edges between outlier nodes (as these go between the added singleton clusters) as well as the number of edges between each outlier node and non-singleton cluster. However, there is still randomness in the assignment of edges between outlier nodes and clustered nodes.

S4.2 Outlier Strategy 2

All the outliers are placed in a single cluster. This strategy is identical to Strategy 1 for how it adds edges between outliers and clustered nodes, but handles outlier-outlier edges differently, as we now describe. The number of edges within the added outlier cluster and the number of edges between each outlier node and the non-singleton clusters in $\mathcal{C}$ are computed. This allows the calculation of the degree of each outlier node within the outlier cluster, and hence also the total number of edges within the outlier cluster. The set of parameters restricted to the outlier cluster (i.e., the within-cluster degree sequence and number of

edges) is used to generate the edges for the outlier cluster using *random_graph* functionality from the *graph_tool* package; this allows for greater randomness than Strategy 1. The remaining edges, between outliers and non-singleton nodes, are added at random for each outlier node and non-singleton cluster from $\mathcal{C}$ in turn. This strategy is more random than Strategy 1 for how it places edges between outlier nodes, but handles edges between outliers and clustered nodes identically as Strategy 1, thus reproducing correctly the number of edges between each outlier node and non-singleton cluster, as in Strategy 1.

S4.3 Outlier Strategy 3

All the outliers are placed in a single cluster, and the parameters from G^* are used to generate a network using SBM. This approach is effectively the same as Strategy 2 for how outlier-outlier edges are generated, but is more random than Strategy 2 for edges between outliers and clustered nodes. Here, we do not retain the number of neighbors each outlier has in each of the non-singleton clusters.

S5 Additional Results on the Training Data

We compare the results of SBM networks from Experiment 1, synthetic networks after applying the first three stages, and both versions of the fourth stage to the SBM networks.

Figure S2 shows the comparison of SBM networks from Experiment 1 against the synthetic networks obtained after applying both the versions of Step 1 of RECCS on those SBM networks.

Fig. S2. Evaluation of Step 1 of RECCS (v1 and v2) compared to baseline SBM networks. Evaluation of the fit of the baseline SBM network and its modified versions produced using Step 1 of the RECCS (v1 and v2) with respect to different criteria are shown for 110 real-world networks and Leiden-CPM clustering at $r = 0.001$ followed by the modified CM pipeline. The Kolmogorov-Smirnov distance is used for the distribution of the number of edges in clusters; simple scalar difference is shown for clustering coefficients, ratios, and mixing parameter; relative difference is shown for diameter; RMSE is shown for degree sequence and minimum edge cut sequence.

S6 Additional Results on the Test Data

In the main paper, we showed results for the RECCS pipeline using parameters obtained on real-world networks with Leiden and IKC clustering methods that were followed by a modification of the CM pipeline that omitted the final step of removing small clusters. Figures S3 and S4 present additional results on these test data that were not provided in the main paper.

Fig. S3. Comparing SBM to the RECCS pipelines on the test networks using Leiden-CPM(0.01)+CM We compare SBM networks to networks produced using the two pipelines, RECCSv1+Outlier Strategies(Step 2) and RECCSv2+Outlier Strategies (Step 2), for different network and clustering statistics. The y-axis shows different distance metrics for various network properties. Error is reported using RMSE for degree sequence, outlier degree sequence, and minimum edge cuts sequence; scalar difference is shown for clustering coefficients and mixing parameter; relative difference is shown for the diameter, number of edges between outliers, and between outliers and clustered nodes. The test networks consist of six real-world networks, each clustered using Leiden-CPM with $r = 0.01$ followed by the modified CM pipeline that omits the final filtering stage.

We tested different combinations of the proposed versions of cluster connectivity enhancing techniques and outlier strategies to observe and understand the pattern of effect of these methods on synthetic networks. We compare the closeness of resultant networks to empirical networks against the closeness of SBM generated networks. For ease of comparison, we have included results for

Fig. S4. Accuracy of SBM and the six RECCS pipelines on test data, using three additional clusterings The test networks consist of six real-world networks, each then clustered using one of three additional clusterings: Leiden-CPM with $r = 0.1$ (top row), Leiden-modularity (middle row), and the Iterative k-core (IKC) method (bottom row), each then post-processed using the modified CM pipeline that omits the final filtering stage. The y-axis shows different distance metrics for various network properties. Error is reported using RMSE for degree sequence, outlier degree sequence, and minimum edge cuts sequence; scalar difference is shown for clustering coefficients and mixing parameter; relative difference is shown for the diameter, number of edges between outliers, and between outliers and clustered nodes.

one of the inspirational clusterings (Leiden optimizing CPM at $r = 0.01$, then post-processed) and combination of both versions of Step 1 of RECCS with selected outlier strategy (Strategy 1) in the main paper. In Figure S3, we show the results of combination of versions of Step 1 of RECCS with all the outlier strategies for this clustering. The results for the remaining three clusterings, for all the RECCS pipelines, are shown here in Figure S4. Each row in the figure corresponds to a specific inspirational clustering mentioned on the right-hand side of the figure.

S7 Results on New Test Data

In this section we present results on new test datasets, obtained on 110 networks but using a different clustering pipeline. Specifically, we employed the Leiden algorithm, optimizing the Constant Potts Model (CPM) at a resolution parameter of $r = 0.01$, followed by a different modification of the Connectivity Modification (CM) pipeline where we omit any filtering for small clusters. Recall that all clustering pipelines in this study use modifications of the CM approach, but the ones in the main paper only omit the final filtering for small clusters, whereas here we omit both the initial and final filtering steps. This adjustment allows the inclusion of all smaller clusters as inputs to the Stochastic Block Model (SBM).

Fig. S5. Accuracy of SBM and the selected RECCS pipeline on new test data. The new test data are 110 networks (same as for the training data) but each clustered using a new pipeline. The new clustering pipeline uses the Leiden-CPM with $r = 0.01$ clustering post-processed using the modified CM pipeline that does not remove small clusters. The y-axis shows different distance metrics for various network properties. Error is reported using RMSE for degree sequence, outlier degree sequence, and minimum edge cuts sequence; scalar difference is shown for clustering coefficients and mixing parameter; relative difference is shown for the diameter, number of edges between outliers, and between outliers and clustered nodes.

The results of the selected RECCS pipelines on the 110 networks are presented in Figure S5. Notably, the observed trends in performance across various network properties remain consistent with those seen in the initial test dataset.

References

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